

VOCATIONAL TRAINING PROGRAMS FOR YOUNG PEOPLE IN KARAKALPAK FOLK PEDAGOGY

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Annotation: This article provides information about programs for training women in the craft of embroidery in Karakalpak folk pedagogy. At the same time, the history, patterns and peculiarities of the sewing of clothes such as "Ko'k ko'yilek" and "Aq jegde", which are considered the national dresses of Karakalpak women, are discussed.

In any country, clothes are distinguished by national costumes, as well as expressing the national uniqueness of the people. Some people have developed them and aroused the interest of the people of the whole world. That is why the distinctiveness of clothes is a national distinctiveness of any nation. Most nations maintain these programs. For example, women in Japan, India, China, Arab countries wear their national clothes regardless of where they go. The distinctiveness of clothing has been preserved since ancient times. The reason is that clothing has matured depending on people's living conditions, nature, variety and changes. For example, the clothes of Karakalpak women are quite different. It is known from historical and ethnographic sources that the program of training girls in the craft of sewing clothes from a young age in the people of Karakalpak was widely established.

Any girl is judged by her handwork. A girl who is going to get married was able to introduce her handcrafts to the people. Well-known ethnographer, professor T.A. Zhdanko said about it: "Teaching girls from the age of 10-14 to weave braids and carve patterns is the best part of the Karakalpak people. The reason is that among the materials of the 18th and 19th centuries, it is difficult to find a girl who does not know how to weave braids and carve patterns on kerchiefs. "Young girls rose to the heights of art competing with each other" [1;117]

"Ko'k ko'yilek", which is one of the unique examples of Karakalpak embroidery art, which is currently kept in museums of the world, is a type of royal dress that cannot be found in any other country. It is also a unique example of painting and embroidery art. "Ko'k ko'yilek" is also called "boyaw ko'yilek" and "kesteli ko'yilek" by Karakalpaks. The reason is that this dress is painted in blue color and decorated with various embroidery. More than 60 types of patterns are used in the decoration of the shirt. The "Ko'k ko'yilek" was very expensive in terms of value and 5 cows were required for its price. The reason is that this dress was decorated with patterns and sewn for 4-5 years. Dark blue dyed gray is decorated with red and yellow threads. These patterns start from the collar, across the chest to the front hem of the shirt and at the ends of the two sleeves. The people living in the villages by the sea or who moved to the coast from this side called the pattern of the blue shirt "sawit nagis" [3; 42]. At the same time, the plain blue color was a sign of grief and mourning in the Karakalpak people. It is said that when Prophet Muhammad died in the war, all his women took his blue clothes and wore them as a dress as a symbol of mourning. Since then, blue clothes have been a symbol of sadness [2;54]. At the same time, in the ancient Turks, the blue color represented the sky, God, the creator of everything. By presenting such old information, we have shown that the "Ko'k ko'yilek", whose origins and wearing periods are not fully determined, can be related to social psychology and religious concepts. Other nations do not have this type of clothing. A shirt with embroidery on the front is found in some Siberian people. But it is interesting that its patterns and color

are called "sawit nagis" in general. This name is mainly related to the ancient massagets who live on the coast of the island. In them, girls rode horses and took part in the war. There are assumptions that the epic "Forty Girls" depicts that period. Therefore, it is not in vain that the kok koylek pattern is called "sawit nagis". The collar of the "kok koylek" is trimmed, and the red shirt is embroidered with a pattern. The front of the "Kok koylek" is divided by several oblique lines, and red, white, and yellow patterns are arranged on these lines. The lower part of these is embroidered with red silk, unlike any other extant Karakalpak jewelry. Their number is different in each blue shirt. For example; There are six in the kok koylek in the museum in Saint-Petersburg (arranged two by three), and three in the kok koylek taken from Karaozek in the Nukus State Museum. The main side is divided into two steps, the ends are vaulted. The lower part is divided into two parts on the outside. On a kok koylek kept in the Museum of Ethnography in St. Petersburg, the diagonal lines are repeated three times. "Bawirsaq gül" is wrapped around both sides of the lowest piece of jewelry. In the second and third rows, only "bawirsaq guller" are lined up and decorated with cross-line and espe patterns. These patterns are the same on the surface in all three ways. The pattern on the upper part of the black collared shirt is larger than the pattern on the lower part. The bottom and sides of the patterns are not bordered by any lines. Like bright stars in a dark night, there is an embroidery of a small triangle in white and red. These tips are called "bawirsaq gul". Although they are not bounded by a line, they are located in a different direction. This piece of kok koylek embroidery is reminiscent of a pattern reminiscent of the starry sky inside the dome of architectural buildings in Central Asia[3;44]. Sa'wkele, a kok koylek made in the style of a silver cap, is also rarely preserved among the people. Now there are 5-6 pieces of blue dress in the museums of the world.

As we said above, after the age of a woman exceeds 40-55 years, the color of her clothes and jewelry changes. Instead of a statue, there is a tumarsha, a bracelet instead of a zirak, and a white jacket instead of a red dress, which are considered to be a sign of people's ethical, aesthetic and social life. It is emphasized that the marking of the stages of human life with the help of colors is a particularly noteworthy aspect of scientific research processes. Only the front side of the white kiymeshek is covered with embroidery, its general structure is the same as the red kiymeshek. The top of the triangular piece is cut off and has a face opening in the middle. The patterns are embroidered in a circular pattern on the lower edge and several vertical patterns are attached to the sleeve. Their number and width will be the same. The pattern on the circular path and the very wide middle path on the steep path are the same, and they form the basis of the pattern process. The large patterns on the front of the white dress are decorated with "Romb", "Atanaq", "Tuye taban" and small "g'az moyin" pattern on the other two sides. The patterns are white gray with additional yellow threads worked with red thread.

A white jegde is a short and tight-fitting, never-to-be-worn wedding dress for women, made of white gray with large embroidery on the collar and outside. The most common type of white eye is "kerege koz". Along its line are small "qos muyiz" with threads of two colors (red and yellow). A large pattern is placed inside the "kerege koz" in some white jegde. There are also white jegdels made of several slanting paths composed of a checkered "bawirsaq gul" combination on a blue shirt.

The back side, both sides of the hems of such jegde are combined in color and pattern with several pieces. In this way, there are mainly three types of patterns on jegde. Kerege ko'z pattern is a very common type. A large plant-like "g'arg'a tuyaq" pattern covers the entire white jacket. The checkered "Ayl nag'is" system found on the blue shirt, mixed with other patterns, organizes it everywhere. They are like jewelry. A white jacket does not wear any ornaments like a blue shirt. The collar is embroidered separately on the white jacket. It has its own look, style, and color, but it's the same color as the white jacket.

Types of patterns, sections, rugs, woodcarving patterns used in Karalpak instructions. But their combined seeds, variations in color enrich each pattern. The patterns in the table are related to population types and their development process. Blue and red, white and blue dyed cloth, dresses made from dresses made from colored threads. He boiled cotton fiber for Makkah. Connect this link. Interestingly, it comes in red.. Bringing the eye painted neck to players in the city. Purchased from a garden in the city or village. Those who make beautiful clothes, those who sell spices.. When he was in a ball, someone would pull him in.. Because he was very kind and kept his tongue in front of his eyes.. With his own room. He was dressed

in twelve layers of white clothes.. Dyed and dried threads of yarn, standing next to the table stitcher. If there are no cash notes drawn on the covers or written on paper. Exemplary exercises, teacher's instructions, author's skills, sharpness of imagination were important.. To the teacher girl, her teacher (mother, guide, etc.) was very important. Therefore, prostitutes' clothes are more expensive than men's clothes, and their clothes themselves require a lot of work.

According to the famous scientist K.. Mambetov, the main reason for this may be in respecting girls and considering them to be preoccupied with beauty.. In this way, we see that our people are implementing the idea of teaching their youth to art from a young age. Attracting young people, especially girls, to the art of needlework is currently a major focus of craft education.

References

1. K. Mambetov. Ethnographic history of the Karakalpaks. Nukus: Karakalpakstan, 1995. Pages 116-117. Add
2. Alevov O' , J. Taspanova. Qaliqnazarova G.Q. History of pedagogical ideas. read the manual. Tashkent. "Yosh Avlod Matbaa", 2022. Page 54
3. A. Allamuratov. An empty legacy. Nukus: "Bilim", 1993. - Pages 42 - 44.